

Carbon Dot/Polypyrrole Nanoparticle Complexes as Multifunctional Theranostic Agents

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Abstract & Methods

Polypyrrole nanoparticles (PPy-NPs) with excellent near-infrared (NIR) absorption have been commonly used as photothermal therapy (PTT) agents. However, PTT using PPy-NPs has limitations in that it is difficult to accurately identify treatment effects. In this study, to overcome these limitations, amine-terminated green carbon dots (G-CDs) with bright green fluorescence properties (λ_{ex} = 380 nm; λ_{em} = 530 nm) are combined with the carboxylated PPy-NPs by EDC/NHS coupling reaction to make a novel PTT-imaging agent. The G-CD/PPy-NP complexes have excellent hydrophilicity and photostability as well as exhibits sufficient photothermal conversion efficiency (η = 42.4 %) to induce apoptosis in tumor. Therefore, the G-CD/PPy-NP complexes can be utilized as theranostic agents by monitoring therapeutic effects in real time.

1. Green carbon dots were synthesized using neutral red and urea.
2. Polypyrrole nanoparticles were conjugated with green carbon dots.
3. G-CDs emit green fluorescence and PPy-NPs convert NIR to heat.

Scheme 1. Bioimaging and photothermal therapy by green carbon dot/polypyrrole nanoparticles.

Results – Characterization

Fig 1. (a) TEM image of the G-CDs. Inset : size distribution of G-CDs. (b) TEM image of the PPy-NPs. (c) TEM image of the G-CD/PPy-NPs.

Fig 2. (a) UV-vis absorption spectrum of the G-CDs, PPy-NPs and G-CD/PPy-NPs in the aqueous solution. (b) Fluorescence spectra of the G-CDs aqueous dispersion under different excitation wavelengths. (c) Fluorescence spectra of the G-CDs and G-CD/PPy-NPs (λ_{ex} = 380 nm).

Results – Photothermal effect & Cell viability

Fig 3. Photothermal properties of D.W., PPy-NPs and G-CD/PPy-NPs. (a) Temperature elevation of D.W. and G-CD/PPy-NPs under a 808 nm laser (1 W cm^{-1}). (b) The temperature change curves of G-CD/PPy-NPs (0.5 mg/mL) during five cycles. (c) Plot of cooling time versus the negative natural logarithm and the corresponding linear fitting curve.

Fig 4. Cell viability of HeLa cells treated with different concentrations of G-CD/PPy-NPs by using MTT assays.

Conclusion

In summary, we demonstrate successful PTT agents by conjugating PPy-NPs and G-CDs. The yield of complexes through EDC/NHS reaction was 27.4%. The complexes emit fluorescence at 530 nm, and the temperature increases to 55.1 °C when irradiated with 808 nm laser (1 W cm^{-1}) to calculate the photothermal conversion efficiency of 42.4%. The cell viability was over 90% up to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Therefore, this complexes have the potentials to simultaneously perform photothermal therapy and bioimaging.

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